

Fluoride induced alterations in erythrocyte and related parameters of an Air-breathing fish, *Channa punctatus* (Bloch)

Sunil Kumar Guru^{1*}, Rajesh Behera² and Milan Kumar Behera³

^{1,3}*Eco-toxicology laboratory, P.G. Department of Zoology, G.M. (Autonomous) College, Sambalpur – 768004, INDIA.*

²*Department of Zoology, Stewart Science College, Cuttack – 753001, INDIA*

E-mail: drsunil.guru@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The effect of various concentrations of fluoride (NaF) (10, 20, 30 and 40ppm) after 15 days of exposure on some haematobiochemical parameters of *Channa punctatus* (Bloch) has been studied. Changes in the shape and size, cell membrane and nucleus of the R.B.C. were observed. Clumping of the R.B.C. cells was noted. Clumping becomes prominent in higher concentrations. The TEC, Hb, PCV, MCV, MCH and MCHC progressively decreased with an increase in the concentration of fluoride. The length/ breadth ratio of erythrocyte and erythrocyte nucleus do not depart significantly from normal values and as such there is no significant change in erythrocyte and nuclear surface area.

Keywords : Fluoride, *Channa Punctatus*, Erythrocyte, Haematological Parameters.

INTRODUCTION

Stress is a general and non-specific response to any factor disturbing homeostasis. Stress in fish may be induced by various abiotic environmental factors, biotic interaction and by human activities. Stress involves various physiological changes including alternation in blood composition. Stress also induces changes in blood cell numbers and activities. In the red cell system – decrease in PCV, Cell count, cell volume and haemoglobin level usually take place. Witeska⁽¹⁾ has reported that intoxication of fish with various heavy metals may cause symptoms similar to the stress reaction.

The fluoride comes from the element fluorine, the 17th most abundant element in the earth's crust which is a gas and never occurs in Free State in nature. Fluorine exists as fluoride compounds which are constituents of materials

in rocks and soil⁽²⁾. Naturally occurring fluorides make up approximately 0.06-0.9% of the earth's crust and form components of rock, clay and soil⁽³⁾. In India high concentration of fluoride (> 1.5mg/l) have been reported from Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Delhi, Gujarat, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu and Kashmir, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Odisha, Punjab, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu and Uttar Pradesh⁽⁴⁾.

The toxic effects of elevated fluoride on various aquatic species has been reported by Camargo⁽⁵⁾. Fluoride affects the haematological parameters⁽⁶⁾, brings about morphological and behavioural changes⁽⁷⁾ and affects the cellular architecture in vertebrates⁽⁸⁾.

The present investigation was undertaken to find out the toxic effects of fluoride on the erythrocyte and related haematological

parameters of a freshwater, air-breathing fish, *Channa punctatus* (Bloch).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Channa punctatus ranging in length from 12-15cm and having a body weight of 30-35gm were obtained from the local freshwater resources and were maintained in large aquaria for 10 days to acclimatize them to the laboratory conditions. Chlorine free deep well water was used which was changed at regular intervals. The values of some of the parameters of the water used were hardness 180ppm; pH – 7.5±0.2; temperature - 25±2c⁰; DO 7.2ppm and alkalinity 115ppm. The fishes were fed daily with chopped earthworms.

The fishes were divided into 5 groups of 20 each, irrespective of their sex. Out of which 4 groups were exposed to 10ppm, 20ppm, 30ppm and 40ppm fluoride respectively. The fifth batches of fishes were maintained as control. The blood samples from the treated as well as control fishes were collected directly from the heart after 15 days. The blood was collected in EDTA coated vials and then processed for the estimation of different parameters under investigation. All the blood parameters were determined employing standard haematological techniques^(9,10). The data were analyzed statistically to test their significance. Analar grade of sodium fluoride, NaF (BDH make) was used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The alternation in erythrocyte and related haematological parameters of the fish *Channa punctatus* exposed to various concentrations of fluoride are presented in Table -1 and plates 1-6 of Figure 1. Few immature erythrocyte cells were noted. The walls of erythrocyte and the nuclear membrane disintegrated. Vacuoles were noted within the erythrocyte cells. There was change in the shape of RBC. The erythrocytes tended to be clumped and showed lobular disposition.

On exposure to various concentrations of fluoride for 15 days a significant decrease of TEC, length and breadth of erythrocytes and their nucleus, ratios of length and breadth of erythrocytes and their nucleus, Hb%, PCV (haematocrit value), MCV, MCH and MCHC were noted (Table – 1).

The reduction in R.B.C. count and Hb% after 15 days of treatment to various doses of fluoride indicates anaemia associated with erythropenia, which has been reported earlier due to exposure of fishes to various other metals⁽¹¹⁻¹⁴⁾. This anaemia may be due to erythropoiesis, faulty haemosynthesis and osmoregulatory dysfunction or due to an increase in the rate of erythrocyte destruction in haemopoietic organs^(15,16). Vutukuru⁽¹³⁾ reported that high concentration of heavy metals bring about a gradual high rate of decrease in R.B.C. count and Hb% as observed during the present investigation.

Parameters	Control	10ppm	20ppm	30ppm	40ppm
TEC × 10 ⁶ /mm ³	3.16± 0.16	3.6±0.06	2.90±0.04	2.76±0.08	2.46±0.04
Length of RBC(mm)	9.86±0.28	9.72±0.24	9.68±0.20	9.58±0.12	9.12±0.14
Breadth of RBC(mm)	8.23±0.22	8.10±0.20	7.86±0.18	7.72±0.16	7.62±0.12
Length of Nucleus(mm)	4.28±0.08	4.06±0.06	3.96±0.06	3.82±0.04	3.62±0.04
Breadth of Nucleus(mm)	3.76±0.06	3.68±0.06	3.56±0.05	3.42±0.04	3.12±0.02
Length/Breadth (RBC)	1.198	1.201	1.232	1.241	1.201
Length/Breadth (Nucleus)	1.138	1.103	1.112	1.117	1.160
Haemoglobin (%)	10.26±0.12	9.86±0.14	9.64±0.12	9.12±0.12	8.62±0.08
PCV (%)	28.64±0.92	27.68±0.86	26.28±0.56	25.88±0.54	24.28±0.42
MCV (mm ³)	102.28±2.42	98.68±2.32	96.24±2.30	95.64±2.10	93.44±1.98
MCH (pg)	30.68±0.66	29.46±0.64	28.76±0.58	27.88±0.52	26.64±0.48
MCHC (%)	5.62±0.24	5.48±0.22	5.12±0.20	4.96±0.18	4.64±0.16

Table 1. Changes in erythrocyte and related parameters in *Channa punctatus* under the stress of fluoride (n=20). Number of erythrocytes considered for length and breadth is 50. All the parameters examined showed significant decrease at 0.01 levels. A change in the length/breadth ratio of erythrocyte and erythrocyte nucleus is non-significant.

Plate 1. Normal untreated blood cells of *channa punctatus*. (1200 X).

Plate 2. After 24 hours treatment with 10ppm fluoride (Disintegration of outer cell membrane). (1600 X).

Plate 3. After 48 hours treatment with 10 ppm fluoride (Initiation of clumping). (1600 X)

Plate 4. After 24 hours treatment with 20ppm fluoride (Prominent clumping of RBCs). (1200 X)

Plate 5. After 48 hours treatment with 20ppm fluoride (Lobular Clumping of RBCs). (1500 X)

Plate 6. After 96 hours treatment with 20ppm fluoride (Disintegration of Nuclear Membrane) (2000 X)

Figure 1. The alteration in erythrocyte and related haematological parameters of the fish *Channa punctatus* exposed to various concentrations of fluoride (Plates 1-6).

Yaji and Auta⁽¹⁷⁾ also observed similar gradual decrease in TEC and Hb% on exposure to increasing concentration of monocrotophos and they attribute this anaemic effect to an inhibition in erythrocyte production and haemodilution. Ololade and Ogini⁽¹⁸⁾ also reported a similar reduction in the values of TEC and Hb% in *Clarias gariepinus* on exposure to various concentrations of zinc. Whereas Alwan *et.al*⁽¹⁹⁾ reported that TEC and Hb% increased when *Tilapia zilli* was exposed to different concentrations of aluminium. Vinodini and Narayan⁽²⁰⁾ also reported an increase in TEC and Hb% in *Cyprinus carpio* exposed to a mixture of Cd, Pb, Cr and Ni.

A gradual decrease in the length and breadth of erythrocyte and the nucleus of the erythrocyte was noted during the present investigation. Benerjee and Banerjee⁽²¹⁾ observed no significant change in the shape of the erythrocyte and its nucleus, when they treated *Heteropneustes fossilis* with LC₅₀ dose of mercury, chromium and zinc chlorides. They also observed that the surface area of R.B.C. increased in ZnCl₂, whereas decreased in HgCl₂ but increased in ZnCl₂ and CrCl₃ treated fish. Banerjee⁽²²⁾ has reported that there was insignificant change in length/ breadth ratio of erythrocytes and its nucleus along with their surface area in *Heteropneustes fossilis* treated with mercuric sulphate. This is in agreement with the present findings.

Gradual decrease in the haematocrit value (PCV), MCV, MCH and MCHC was noted in the present investigation. Benerjee and Banerjee⁽²¹⁾ reported decreased PCV and MCHC in CrCl₃ and ZnCl₂ treated *Heteropneustes fossilis*, which is in agreement with the present findings. The decrease in these parameters might be associated with haemolysis. Ololade and Oigni⁽¹⁸⁾ observed a decrease in MCHC with increased concentration of toxicant (zinc). Alwan *et.al*⁽¹⁹⁾ while working on the stress of aluminum on the blood of *Tilapia zilli* observed increase in MCHC and MCH and decrease in MCV. Sen *et.al*⁽²³⁾ and Nanda and Behera⁽²⁴⁾ have reported a similar decrease in MCH, MCHC and MCV in fresh water fishes exposed

to zinc and nickel respectively. Vutukuru⁽¹³⁾ has reported a decrease in MCH in chromium treated *Labeo rohita*.

Banerjee⁽²²⁾ recorded a few immature erythrocytes in mercury treated *Heteropneustes fossilis* which is in agreement with the present findings. Banerjee and Banerjee⁽²¹⁾ did not notice any significant change in the erythrocyte of *Heteropneustes fossilis* treated with ZnCl₂, HgCl₂ and CrCl₃. Vacuolization in the cytoplasm of erythrocyte as observed in the present investigation, was also observed by Baltova and Veleheva⁽²⁵⁾ in *Alburnus* treated with Pb, Zn and Cd.

Blood parameters are considered as pathophysiological indicators of the whole body and therefore are important in diagnosing the structural and functional status of fish exposed to toxicants. A number of haematological indices are used to assess the functional status of the oxygen carrying capacity of the blood stream and have been used as indicator of metal pollution in the aquatic environment⁽¹²⁾. In conclusion, biological survey seems to be more advantageous than physicochemical survey for continuous environmental pollution surveillance and in this respect representative fish species seem to be the most sensitive bio-indicator of even subtle changes in the ecosystem.

REFERENCES

1. Witeska, M. 2005: stress in fish – haematobiological and immunological effects of heavy metals; *Elect. J. Ichthyol.* : 1:35-41.
2. Dhar, V and M. Bhatnagar 2009: Physiology and toxicity of fluoride; *Indian J. Dent. Res.* **20(3)** : 350-355.
3. Agency for toxic Substances and Disease Registry (ATSDR), 2003: Toxicological profile for fluorides. Hydrogen Fluorides and fluorine, U.S. Department of Health and Human Services, Atlanta, U.S.
4. Susheela, A.K. 2001: Fluorosis : Indian scenario, "Treatise on fluorosis"; Fluorosis Research and Rural Development Foundation, Pp. 13-15.

5. Camargo, J.A. 2003: Fluoride toxicity to aquatic organisms; A review; *Chemosphere*, **50(3)**: 251-264.
6. Saxena, R; R. Gupta; M. Tripathy and K. Gopal 2001: fluoride induced haematological alterations in freshwater fish, *Channa punctatus*. *J. Ecophysiol, Occup. Hlth.* **1**: 139-146.
7. Tripathi, A.;A. Kumar : A. Rani and M. Tripathy 2004; Fluoride induced morphological and behavioural changes in freshwater fish, *Channa punctatus*; *J. Ecophysical. Occup, Hlth*; **4**: 83-88.
8. Gupta, R.2003: Pathophysiological consequence to freshwater fish, *Channa punctatus* induced by fluoride, Ph.D, dissertation, University of Lucknow, Lucknow.
9. Decie, J.V. and S.M. Lewis, 2001: "Practical Haematology", 9th edition Churchill and Livingstone, London, Pp. 663.
10. Yadav, D.P. and V. Banerjee 1985: Erythrocyte morphology and abundance in peripheral blood of three species of *Channa*; *J. Adv. Zool.*; **6**: 68-73.
11. Agrawal, V.P.: K. Sandhya and K.A. Goel, 1983: Lithium induced haematobil chemical changes in snake headed fish, *Channa punctatus*, *Ind. J. Zootomy.*; **10**:97-100.
12. Shah, S.L.: and A. Altindag 2004: Haematological parameters of Tench (*Tinca tinca* L.) after acute and chronic exposure to lethal and sub-lethal mercury treatments; *Bull. Environ. Contam. Toxicol* : **73** : 911-918.
13. Vutukuru, S.S. 2005 : Acute effects of Hexavalent chromium on survival, oxygen consumption, haematological parameters, and some biochemical profiles of the Indian major carp, *Labeo rohita*; *Int. J. environ. Res. Public Health.*; **2(3)** : 456-462.
14. Ramesh, M. and M. Saravanan 2008: Haematological and biochemical responses in freshwater fish. *Cyprinus carpio* exposed to chloropyrifos.; *I.J.I.B.*; **3(1)** : 80-83.
15. Jenkins, F.; J. Smith *et.al*, 2003: Effect of sub-lethal concentration of endosulfan on haematological and serum biochemical parameters in the carp. *Cyprinus carpio*; *Environ, Contam, Toxicol*; **70**: 943-947.
16. Seth, N. and K.K. Saxena 2003: Haematological responses in a freshwater fish, *Channa punctatus* due to fanvalerate; *Bull. Environ. Contam, Toxicol.*; **71** : 1192-1199.
17. Yaji, A.J. and Auta, J. (2007): Sub-lethal effects of monocrotophos on some haematological indices of African Catfish, *Clarias gariepinus* (*Teungels*) ; *J. Fish . Intl.*; **2(1)**:115-117.
18. Ololade, I.A., and Oginni, O. (2009): Behavioural and haematological effects of Zinc on African Cat fish, *Clarias gariepinus*, *Intl. J. Fish. Aquat.*; **1(2)**: 22 – 27.
19. Alwan, S.F.; Hadi, A.A. and Shokr, A. E. (2009): Alterations in haematological parameters of freshwater fish, *Tilapia zilli*, exposed to aluminium; *J. Sci. Appl.*; **3(1)**: 12 – 19.
20. Vinodhini, R. and Narayanan, M. (2009): the impact of toxic heavy metal on the haematological parameters in common carp (*Cyprinus carpio*); *Iran. J. Health Sci.Engg.*; **6(1)**: 23 – 28.
21. Banerjee, V. and M. Banerjee, (1988): Effect of heavy metal poisoning on peripheral heamogram in *Heteropneustes fossilis* (Bloch)exposed to Murcury, Chromium and Zinic Choride(LC₅₀) *Comp.Physiol.Ecol*; **13(2)**: 128 -134.
22. Banerjee, V. (1985): Effect of heavy metal poisoning on peripheral heamogram in *Heteropneustes fossilis* (Bloch); treated with Murcuric sulphate(LC₅₀) *Comp.Physiol.Ecol*; **11(4)**: 173 -176.
23. Sen, G.; Behera, M.K. and Patel, P.N. (1992): Effect of zinc on haemato-biochemical parameters of *Channa punctatus*; *J. Ecotoxicol. Environ. Monit.*; **2**:89-92.
24. Nanda, P. and Behera, M.K. (1996): Nickel induced changes in some haemato-biochemical parameter of a Catfish, *Heteropneustes fossilis* (Bloch); *Enviorn and Ecol.*; **14(1)**: 82 – 85.
25. Baltova,S. and I. Velcheva(2005):Some morphological and pathological modification of the blood cells of *Alburnus alburnus* in intoxication with heavy metal (Pb, Zn and Cd); proceedings of the Balkan Scientific Conference of Biology in Plovdiv(Bulgaria)Pp:461-467.

DOI:

<https://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7248374>

Received: 13 October 2014;

Accepted; 28 November 2014;

Available online : 17 December 2014

